

NAVIGATING DIGITAL PRESERVATION IN THE CLOUD: LESSONS, STRATEGIES, AND GOOD PRACTICES

Nathan Tallman

University of Virginia /
Academic Preservation Trust
United States
nathan.tallman@aptrust.org
0000-0002-5308-4100

Flavia Ruffner

University of Virginia /
Academic Preservation Trust
United States
flavia.ruffner@aptrust.org
0009-0005-2050-5369

Eric Lopatin

University of California /
California Digital Library
United States
eric.lopatin@ucop.edu
0000-0002-5296-1116

Terrence Brady

University of California /
California Digital Library
United States
terrence.brady@ucop.edu
0000-0002-2411-9845

Abstract – This interactive workshop explored successful strategies for cloud-based digital preservation, focusing on cost management, fixity, replication, and DevOps workflows. Through breakout discussions and real-time documentation, participants collaboratively developed a set of “good practices” to navigate preservation in the cloud. Attendees gained practical insights and contributed to a shared resource for ongoing community use.

Submission Type – Workshop.

Keywords – Fixity, Cost Model, Workflows, Cloud Computing, DevOps

Conference Topics – Haerenga – Journey.

I. INTRODUCTION

As digital preservation increasingly moves to cloud environments, practitioners face opportunities and challenges in managing costs, ensuring integrity, and leveraging cloud-native capabilities without vendor lock-in. This interactive iPRES 2025 workshop built upon the discussions from the iPRES 2024 session, "Implications of Cloud Adoption for Digital Preservation," which raised significant concerns—particularly around cost—regarding digital preservation in the cloud [1]. In response, this workshop brought together professionals with

decades of collective experience in cloud-based digital preservation to share lessons learned and collaboratively develop a community-driven list of “good practices.” [2]

Through plenary discussions, breakout sessions, and real-time documentation, participants explored key topics including FinOps (cost management), containerization, fixity, replication, task queues, security, and DevOps workflows. The breakout discussions contributed to a shared, open document that evolved throughout the session, capturing practical strategies and insights [2].

The workshop concluded with a collective review of the emerging “good practices” list, identifying major takeaways and opportunities for ongoing refinement beyond iPRES 2025. Attendees left with new knowledge and a tangible, collaboratively built resource to inform their cloud-based preservation strategies.

II. WORKSHOP GOALS AND TARGET AUDIENCE

1) Share practical experiences and lessons learned in cloud-based digital preservation.

2) Discuss strategies to manage costs effectively while leveraging cloud-native features and avoiding vendor lock-in.

3) Foster participant engagement through shared stories and collaborative discussions.

4) Develop a collaboratively created and openly accessible list of “good practices” for digital preservation in the cloud.

The target audience comprised digital preservation practitioners, archivists, librarians, IT professionals, and others interested in or already using cloud services for digital preservation.

III. FORMAT AND ACTIVITIES

A. Opening Session

The workshop began with an overview of key considerations in cloud-based digital preservation, setting the stage for deeper discussions. Participants were invited to share their experiences and challenges with cloud services, helping shape the breakout sessions' focus. Facilitators also introduced the collaborative “Good Practices” document, a shared resource to which all groups contributed throughout the session, ensuring that insights and strategies were captured in real time.

B. Facilitated Breakout Sessions

Participants engaged in three rounds of 20-minute breakout discussions, allowing them to explore multiple topics. In real time, each group directly contributed key insights and recommendations to the shared “Good Practices” document [2].

Participants moved between breakout groups across the three sessions, ensuring broad engagement with different aspects of cloud-based digital preservation.

C. Breakout Categories

- 1) Budget, Finance, FinOps – Cost management and financial planning strategies in cloud environments.
- 2) Preservation Activities – Approaches to replication, file format conversion, metadata extraction, fixity, integrity, and authenticity.
- 3) DevOps – Best practices for estimating and queuing workloads, security measures, and system monitoring.

IV. COLLABORATIVE GOOD PRACTICES DEVELOPMENT

Each breakout group contributed key points, lessons learned, and recommendations to the shared digital document, which all workshop attendees could edit and expand in real time. Serving as a living reference, this document consolidates collective expertise and strategies, ensuring that insights gained during the session remain accessible and continue to evolve beyond the workshop [2].

V. CLOSING SESSION

After the breakout sessions, participants reconvened as a large group to review key highlights from the collaborative “Good Practices” document [2]. Facilitators lead a discussion on emerging themes and insights, encouraging reflection on shared strategies. The session concluded with a discussion of next steps, exploring how participants can continue refining and applying the document beyond the workshop.

VI. CONCLUSION

This workshop was a hands-on, collaborative space for practitioners to share experiences, learn from each other, and co-develop a valuable resource for the community. The collaborative “Good Practices” document ensures that insights gathered during the session have a lasting impact, serving as a shared guide for digital preservation professionals navigating the cloud [2].

REFERENCES

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AUTHOR BIOGRAPHIES

Nathan Tallman is the Executive Director of Academic Preservation Trust, overseeing community-owned digital preservation services. He previously served as Digital Preservation Librarian at Penn State University and Digital Content Strategist at the University of Cincinnati. Tallman holds an MLS and a BS in Business Administration from the University at Buffalo.

Flavia Ruffner is the DevSecOps Engineer for Academic Preservation Trust, with over two decades of experience developing and managing enterprise systems in legacy and cloud environments. She holds a BIS from the University of Virginia, an MSAIT, and a Cyber Security Certificate from George Mason University's Engineering School.

Eric Lopatin is the Product Manager for California Digital Library's digital preservation initiatives, including the Merritt repository, which preserves library special collections content and research publications from all ten University of California campuses. He previously managed several publishing-related systems at the Public Library of Science.

Terrence Brady is a software developer for the California Digital Library, and Terry is the technical lead for the Merritt digital preservation repository. Terry has also built applications for the Georgetown University Library, LexisNexis, and the National Archives and Records Administration.

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